

MAQOM AND ITS PRESENT DAY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the art and concept of maqom, as well as its future in the present day.*

Keywords: *maqom, music, classical, creativity, east, gathering.*

МАКОМ И ЕГО СОВРЕМЕННОСТЬ

Аннотация. *В этой статье обсуждается искусство и концепция макама, а также его будущее в наши дни.*

Ключевые слова: *маком, музыка, классика, творчество, восток, собрание.*

Maqom (in Arabic - place, space, place) is one of the main concepts in the music of the Muslim East. Initially, this concept meant a place or a fret that is pressed to produce a sound of a certain pitch on a stringed instrument. Over time, in the process of developing the theory of Eastern music, the meaning of maqom expanded and became a concept that included a certain fret structure, system, form, genre, musical directions and performance styles. The prominent representatives of the theory of classical music of the Muslim East, Abu Yusuf al-Kindi, Al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Ibn Zayla, Safiuddin al-Urmawi, Mahmud al-Sherazi, Abdulkadir Maroghi and other scholars, deeply studied the musical and aesthetic aspects of the maqom and presented their theoretical explanations.

The number and system of maqoms were not clearly defined in the classical music of the Near and Middle East until the 13th century. Safiuddin al-Urmawi developed a scientific classification of maqoms and created the “Twelve Maqom System”. This system was used until the 17th century, and on its basis national and local maqom types and styles were formed in different regions. Today, Uzbeks and Tajiks call it “maqom”, Turkmen and Uyghurs “muqam”, Iranians and Azerbaijanis “dastgoh”, Turks “makam”, and Arab peoples “maqam”.

The art of maqom in the East

The art and performance styles of the Eastern peoples have been enriched over the centuries by the influence of folk, national local traditions. In Uzbek classical music, the Bukhara Shashmaqom, Khorezm maqoms, Fergana-Tashkent maqom paths, surnay, dutar maqom paths

have been formed and have survived to this day. The maqom instrument and ashula paths constitute a significant part of the national musical heritage and have served as a source of inspiration for the creativity of composers.

Modern development of maqom art

Since the beginning of the 20th century, Uzbek composers have effectively used maqom styles, expressing national melodies and tones in modern musical genres. Haji Abdulaziz, Sodirkhon Hafiz, Yu. The melodies and songs of such artists as Rajabiy and F. Sodiqov, as well as works such as V. Uspensky's "Farhod and Shirin", R. Glier and T. Sodiqov's musical drama "Layli and Majnun", and M. Ashrafi's opera "Dilorom" were created on the basis of maqom. The art of maqom is being revived artistically and aesthetically and is gaining significant importance in the process of modern music.

Scientific research and educational work on maqom

Many scientific and creative conferences and symposiums dedicated to the art of maqom have been held, including international musicological symposia in Samarkand (1978, 1983, 1987, 2001), Berlin (1988), Finland (1996) and Istanbul (1999). Scientific theoretical and practical knowledge on maqom art is taught in primary, secondary specialized and higher educational institutions of the country, and qualified specialists are being trained. Since 1987, the scientific group "Maqom" of the International Union for Traditional Music under UNESCO has been operating.

The current logo of the Uzbek National Center for Maqom Art

The Uzbek National Center for Maqom Art was established by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3391 dated November 17, 2017. The center operates with the aim of supporting the art of maqom, its study and development, conducting scientific research, attracting and teaching the younger generation to maqom music, and increasing the prestige and importance of Uzbek maqom art internationally. Based on Resolution No. PQ-112 of February 2, 2022, regional branches of the center were established, which made it possible to further expand the development of maqom art and teach ancient and modern forms of national music in all regions.

Logo of the International Conference on Maqom Art

The International Conference on Maqom Art is held twice a year in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3391 dated November 17, 2017. This conference is an important mechanism for discussing the art of Maqom, its historical and

modern forms, conducting international scientific exchanges, and conducting major research on Maqom art.

The First International Conference on Maqom Art was held at a high artistic level on September 6-10, 2018 in the city of Shahrisabz, Kashkadarya region. About 300 prominent musicologists, scholars, specialists, and performers from 73 countries participated in this conference. The Second International Conference on Maqom Art was held on June 27-30, 2024 in the Zamin district of Jizzakh region under the auspices of UNESCO and ICESCO. More than 400 participants from more than 80 countries attended the conference. During the conferences, maqom performance styles, teaching methodologies, and prospects for the international development of maqom music will be discussed. The maqom conference will also host an international competition, where participants will demonstrate their skills in performing maqom.

In accordance with the resolution of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev “On holding the International Maqom Art Conference” signed on April 6, 2018, residents and guests of our country will witness this prestigious event from September 6 to 10. At the moment, the venue of the conference - Shahrisabz - is experiencing the glory of maqom art.

During his visit to the Kashkadarya region, the Head of State visited the Oqsaroy, built by our great grandfather Amir Temur, and noted that Shahrisabz is the most suitable place to spread our ancient heritage of maqoms to the world. After all, the period when “Shashmaqom” was born is closely connected with the history of the statehood of Amir Temur.

There are many sources that indicate that during the time of our great grandfather, the art of music developed rapidly and experienced a real revival, and that musicianship and singing, music science and composition reached perfection. They state that by the 17th-18th centuries, groups of dancers and musicians were formed in Shahrisabz, who danced to the tunes of “Shashmaqom” in collaboration with masters of art from Bukhara and Samarkand. On the occasion of the conference, Hafiz musicians, tourists and other guests from many countries are visiting Shahrisabz. This indicates that the number of people interested in this art and our country is growing worldwide. According to the latest data, 22 musicologists, 29 soloists and musical groups, 21 specialists and honorary guests from foreign countries have expressed their desire to participate in the art festival.

In accordance with the decision of our President, the Shahrisabz branch of the Uzbek National Center for Maqom Art was established within the framework of this conference. Guests arriving in Shahrisabz will receive all the information they are interested in through animated

exhibition tools about the history of Maqom in the Museum of Maqom Art organized in the city Palace of Culture. They will also follow the conference on a large screen operating online in the city's Navruz Park of Culture and Recreation and on the boulevard on the territory of the Dor tilovat complex.

Today, Shahrisabz is truly becoming an international maqom center. Of course, this, in turn, serves to introduce our country and the Uzbek maqom art to the world, and to draw the attention of the world to Uzbekistan.

In November 2003, “Shashmaqom” was recognized by UNESCO as a “Masterpiece of the Oral and Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity”. In 2008, it was included in the World Representative List.

A great monument of the past, Shahrisabz is one of the ancient, famous cities located on the Great Silk Road. Shahrisabz is located 80 kilometers south of Samarkand, in the Takhta-Karacha mountain range. Today, the city has many architectural monuments. Its historical center is included in the UNESCO World Cultural Heritage List. This city is also known as the birthplace of the great commander and conqueror Amir Temur. Previously, Shahrisabz was the capital of the ancient Sogdian state, called Kesh. It was a center of culture, trade, and crafts. A number of wonderful works are being carried out for the present and future of the maqom.

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